

D3.2 | Testing Procedures Specifications Including Test Matrix

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Document Approval

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Nomenclature & Abbreviations

CFU	Colony-forming unit
DPU	Danube Private University, Krems, AT
GUF	Goethe Universität Frankfurt, DE
INM	INM Neuromed, Italia
Log	Log reduction is a measure of how thoroughly a decontamination process reduces the concentration of a contaminant.
MDM	MDM Projects, Israel
NO _x	Nitrogen oxide
O ₃	Ozone
S3 laboratory	Safety level 3 laboratory
VILL	Villinger GmbH, Mieders, AT

Executive Summary

In this CleanAir deliverable the future testing methodology and procedures have been developed and are outlined which has to be followed within WP4. The testing required for final verification and validation of the product is worked out in the deliverable to determine whether products meet the requirements and specifications and that they fulfil their intended purpose. The deliverable is setting the standards and content of a future quality management system. Testing needs, standards and procedures are diversified in this deliverable for different testing procedures performed by the different consortium partners. VILL will be responsible for production end control and that the delivered product will meet all the required properties and features of a technical medical product. Laboratory testing for reduction of virus content in air will be performed by the partner GUF. Final field testing will be performed by INM and DPU in medical treatment rooms.

1. Work Package and Task this Deliverable Relates to

1.1. WP3: Analysis of requirements, developing a testing methodology and a test matrix and definition of materials

1.1.1. Task 3.2: Define and develop the testing methodology (M1 – M3) (INM, DPU, VILL)

In this task existing testing methodologies/procedures will be studied and a methodology will be developed to be followed within WP 4. Task will define all the testing vectors needed for final verification and validation of the product. The goal is to determine whether products meet the requirements and specifications and that they fulfil their intended purpose. They are critical components of a quality management system.

- Verification requirements (whether the products comply with regulations, requirements, specifications)
- Validation (whether the products meet the needs of the end consumer or customer and other stakeholders)
- Testing procedures (functional testing, usability testing, safety and performance testing, usability testing)
- Production end control (define testing procedures for production end control, reliability and durability testing)
- Establishment of a test matrix

2. Verification and Validation requirements by the producer of the CleanAir device (VILL)

The producer of the devices (VILL) has to ensure that the products fully comply with regulations, requirements and specifications set for medical technical equipment and whether they will meet the requirements of the end-users. A detailed list of such tests, which are required, is outlined below:

Master Validation & Verification Plan (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Test Protocols (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Safety Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
EMC Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Transportation Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Microbiological (Demonstration of a 4 log reduction) Test Protocol
Microbiological (effectiveness against representative gram positive and gram negative) Test Protocol
Microbiological (effectiveness against representative COVID-19) Test Protocol (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Reliability Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Labeling Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Functional Validation Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Air Turbulancing Validation Test Outline / Smoke Test (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget)
Dimensional Verification Test Outline (acceptance criteria, sample size, budget, tolerance distribution analysis)

Table 1: Required tests to comply with regulations, requirements and specifications for medical technical equipment

An analysis of the required functional specifications of the final product has to be performed before the test plan above can be executed and completed and the resulting product testing values which are obtained have to be analyzed if they fulfill the below defined values and condition:

Marketing Requirements
Analysis of the competitor's landscape
Finalizing preliminary marketing requirements
Defining product design to be developed
Detailed Technical Requirements
Safety Requirements
Functionality Requirements
Mechanical Requirements
Electronic Requirements
Regulatory Requirements (labeling, disinfection, documentation)
Microbiological Requirements
Cleaning requirements
Installation requirements
Maintenance requirements

Table 2: List of required functional specifications of the final product

3. Verification Requirements & Procedures in field testing (INM and DPU)

At DPU's installation site the following tests are foreseen: germ content in air, particle and aerosol content in air, determination of emitted gases (O₃, NO_x, etc.)

Tests will be conducted in a dental treatment room with-, and without patients and a dental medical doctor, as a function of operating time of the device and in relation to the device emitting area. Reference values will be determined before the device is set into operation. Further test will be conducted to determine the effectiveness of the device depending on installation sites (walls, ceiling) and the effectiveness of the device attached to-, or near the treatment lamp of the dental chair.

At INM tests will be carried out by performing air quality tests using the "ceiling tiles" installation at three different sites of installation, namely a room of 16 m² with one window (site INM1), a room of the same size without windows (site INM2) and in a waiting room of 16 m² (site INM3). For the first two cases, the tests will be performed with-, and without patients and medical doctor. All the measurements will be performed as a function of operating time of the device, of number of people in the room and in relation to the device emitting area. Reference values will be determined before the device is set into operation and additional comparisons will be done between the measurements obtained without people inside the rooms and those obtained with people inside. All these tests will be carried out for a period of two weeks for each installation site. The measurements will include:

- Air microbiology;
- Particle control;
- Surfaces microbiology.

Figure 1 shows the technical details about the installation sites, while in Figures 2,3 and 4 the real pictures of the selected environments are shown. All the rooms have a height of about 265 cm.

Figure 1: Planimetry of the selected installation sites

Figures 2,3,4: Real pictures of the selected testing environments. INM1 (left), INM2 (middle), INM3 (right)

Figure 5: Shows the existing ceiling system.

The dimension of each ceiling panel is 360 cm² (60 cm * 60 cm) and the distance between the panel surface and the ceiling is about 40 cm.

4. Verification & validation of the performance of the CleanAir device

for Covid19 (GUF)

Specific testing for the efficiency of the CleanAir devices against COVID 19 Virus can only be performed in a specific set up laboratory environment which has to fulfill class 3 safety precautions.

The laboratory tests are to be carried out by partner GUF in their S3 laboratory in quantitative suspension tests according to DGHM (German Society for Hygiene and Microbiology) specifications. For this purpose, virus suspension is applied to test surfaces (e.g. stainless steel discs, plastic ware) and is dried at room temperature. Then the test specimens are exposed to the CleanAir system for defined periods of time or remain untreated (positive control). Dried virus suspension is resuspended in a culture medium.

For analyzing replication competence or inactivation of the SARS-CoV-2 virus particles, a cell culture model based on human colon adenocarcinoma cells (Caco-2) will be used. This cell line is a well characterized adherent epithelia cell line and the cells are tested negative for EBV, HBV, HCV, HHV-8, HIV, HTLV-I/II, MLV and SMRV and are constantly tested for mycoplasma. The cells are obtained from the DSMZ (German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Culture GmbH) as frozen culture.

Reduction assay for aerosols is carried out in a specially built test box. Aerosols (<5µm) containing SARS-CoV-2 are generated with a nebulizer and are introduced into the test chamber. If necessary, movement of the air can be simulated by small ventilator. Then the aerosols are exposed to the CleanAir system for defined periods of time and with different pre-defined operating voltages of the system. For positive control, in a number of tests, the aerosols will remain untreated in order to evaluate the deposition-, and inactivation rate by the CleanAir system. After treatment sampling is performed by swab of the test chamber surface. Swab is resuspended in culture medium. End-point limiting dilution assay is performed and viral titer is quantified by the method of Spearman and Kaerber. Logarithmic reduction factor is calculated. Further quantification of replicating virus can be carried out by quantitative RT-PCR.

4.1. System Description for Laboratory Tests

4.1.1. Main Component 1: Ionization Electrode(s)

The first main component the CleanAir system relies on is the ionization electrode. Depending on system configuration and required deposition power the test buildup and later CleanAir system may feature one-, or several ionization electrodes. An ionization electrode is formed by a plastic grid or panel, with a special flock coating applied, comprising a number of electrode tips aligned perpendicular to the electrode surface. The electrode tips are connected to a power supply via a high-impedance resistor. These electrode tips are formed by a special flock material, which is applied by means of electrostatic flocking. The flocks are applied to a conductive polymer layer, which functions both as an adhesive and as a power supply for the flocks. This structure is applied to a plastic grid or panel (substrate material). The substrate material will be replaced after every test run.

4.1.2. Main Component 2: Collector Electrode(s)

In addition to the ionization electrode, a collector electrode is required which forms the opposite pole to the ionization electrode so that the ionized and polarized particles from the air are deposited on it and adhere to it. This collector electrode is formed by an aluminium grid or panel.

4.1.3. Main Component 3: Auxiliary Virucide System(s)

In case the deposition-, and inactivation rates of the system featuring only the ionization-, and deposition electrodes are insufficient, it is planned to combine the deposition electrode with an auxiliary virucide system. Besides other measures, including UV-C light or disinfectant liquids, the preferred variant would feature a surface heating system which would be brought to a temperature of 90°C at regular intervals, for a defined period of time, in order to ensure cyclic inactivation of the viruses collected on the deposition electrode. The relatively high temperature of 90°C should reduce the required activation time of the panel heating to a minimum. The heating technology used

would be a heating system from Villinger, which is applied to the underside of the deposition electrode.

4.2. Test Setup in the S3 Laboratory

The S3 test chamber allows a maximum size of the test box of 800 long x 300 deep x 400 mm high. The test box will be made of plexiglass and will have a removable front door for easy handling. To perform the planned tests, the housing and the door must be fitted with a seal. The high voltage generators which provide voltage to the ionization electrodes should be quickly and easily replaceable with connectors. The 12V voltage supply can be provided laterally through a cable bushing. The power supply units can be placed outside the test box, but these, as well as all other samples and equipment, will be disposed of after completion of all tests. A PC fan can be connected with 230V directly in the test chamber. This is to ensure a constant turbulence over all test periods. It is important to make sure that the air flows onto the system. The nebulizer must be filled in the S3 chamber and then placed in the test box. The switch of the nebulizer and the other electrical devices must be moved to the outside. This requires a modification of the commercially available nebulizer. The heating elements can be connected to the existing 230V sockets in the S3 test chamber.

Figure 6: Schematic visualization of “U-shape” and “U-shape heated”

Figure 7: Schematic visualization of “Grid unheated”

Figure 8: Schematic visualization of “Grid heated”

4.3. Test Matrix

Test No.		Configuration	Cycle Time	Input Voltage	
				Ionization Electrode	Collector Electrode
System Calibration					
Test 0	Test 0	U-shape heated	30min	-10 kV	GND
Phase 1					
Test 1	Test 1.1	U-shape heated	180min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 1.2	U-shape heated	120min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 1.3	U-shape heated	60min	-10 kV	GND
Test 2	Test 2.1	U-shape	180min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 2.2	U-shape	120min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 2.3	U-shape	60min	-10 kV	GND
Test 3	Test 3.1	Grid heated	180min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 3.2	Grid heated	120min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 3.3	Grid heated	60min	- 20 kV	GND
Test 4	Test 4.1	Grid	180min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 4.2	Grid	120min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 4.3	Grid	60min	- 20 kV	GND
Test 5	Test 5.1	Grid	180min	- 20 kV	-10kV
	Test 5.2	Grid	120min	- 20 kV	-10kV
	Test 5.3	Grid	60min	- 20 kV	-10kV
Verification					
-	-	X	Xmin	- X kV	X
Phase 2 (optional - in case of successful Phase 1)					
Test 6	Test 6.1	U-shape heated	30min	-10 kV	GND

	Test 6.2	U-shape heated	10min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 6.3	U-shape heated	5min	-10 kV	GND
Test 7	Test 7.1	U-shape	30min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 7.2	U-shape	10min	-10 kV	GND
	Test 7.3	U-shape	5min	-10 kV	GND
Test 8	Test 8.1	Grid heated	30min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 8.2	Grid heated	10min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 8.3	Grid heated	5min	- 20 kV	GND
Test 9	Test 9.1	Grid	30min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 9.2	Grid	10min	- 20 kV	GND
	Test 9.3	Grid	5min	- 20 kV	GND
Test 10	Test 10.1	Grid	30min	- 20 kV	-10kV
	Test 10.2	Grid	10min	- 20 kV	-10kV
	Test 10.3	Grid	5min	- 20 kV	-10kV
Setting Standard Value for Virus Contamination					
	-	-	180min	-	-
	-	-	120min	-	-
	-	-	60min	-	-
	-	-	30min	-	-
	-	-	10min	-	-
	-	-	5min	-	-

Table 3: Preliminary test matrix for laboratory testing @ GUF

5. Validation Requirements & Procedure in field testing (INM, DPU)

At DPU the patient, dentist and dental assistant will be interviewed concerning their personal assessment and experience with the device in operation, safety and other requirements, optical appearance, possible obstructions caused by the device attached to or at the patient treating lamp, possible preferences and device acceptance will be investigated. The general experience of DPU with medical equipment will be researched and determined and their requirements for generating customer satisfaction.

At INM validation will be carried out using questionnaires administered to medical doctors and patients. These questionnaires will be different between medical doctors and patients. The questionnaires for the patients will include only questions about the personal experience with the device, about the noise eventually generated by the device, the appearance and so on. The questionnaires for medical doctors will include, rather than the same questions as in the patient's questionnaire, also other questions more technical, such as the efficacy about the site of the installation, the level of usability of the system, and so on.

6. Detailed Field-Testing Procedures (Functional & Performance, Usability) (INM and DPU)

Testing the air quality by applying the CleanAir device is of particular interest. This interest stems from

the awareness that airborne microorganisms have, like the classically measured chemical pollutants, potential harmful effects on the health of individuals. All types of microorganisms can be present in the air and on surfaces: bacteria, fungi and protozoa, as well as some viruses capable of resisting in an external medium. Particles of microbial origin (toxins, cell fragments, allergens, volatile organic compounds) and plants (pollen) also spread through the air.

The level of microbial contamination of the air in the rooms is proportional to the number of people present, their behavior as well as the characteristics of the ventilation system; it is therefore important that the organizational-management requirements are respected. The determination of the microbial load in the air in the ready room represents a system for assessing whether the set of microbiological risk prevention measures (both plants, organizational and behavioral) are active and, above all, if they are applied correctly. The determination of the microbial load in the air in the operating room represents a system to determine if the proposed device is able to contain the airborne contamination within acceptable levels for the safety of operators and operands.

Thus, for the mentioned reason several tests will be carried out into selected three environments:

1. A medical room with one window, in order to test if the device is able to maintain a good quality of air in a site where there is "natural air circulation" (INM1);
2. A medical room with one window, in order to test if the device is able to maintain a good quality of air in a site where there is no air circulation and the air is stale (INM2);
3. A waiting room, in order to test if CleanAir device is able to maintain a good quality of the air in a place where the flow of people is intense (INM3).

The tests that will be carried out during two weeks in all the three sites of installation and will be of three typologies:

AIR MICROBIOLOGY: Air sampling in 2 points in at rest, air sampling in 1 point in operation for a total of 14 points with the mesophilic count with PERIODICITY before and after positioning the CleanAir device;

PARTICLE CONTROL: Sampling of the airborne particles pursuant to UNI EN ISO 14644 for the determination of the class they belong to in "at rest" and the "Recovery Time" associated with the single room with PERIODICITY before and after positioning the CleanAir device;

SURFACES MICROBIOLOGY: Sampling on 4 surfaces and for a total of 4 points for the determination of: Mesophilic count, yeasts and molds, Staphylococci coagulase +, Enterobacteriaceae, Klebsiella, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas a. (gram negative bacteria) with PERIODICITY before and after positioning the CleanAir device.

All these tests will be carried out by a specialized and certified company.

Environment	SURFACES MICROBIOLOGY- Before and after CleanAir placement	AIR MICROBIOLOGY AT REST- Before and after CleanAir placement	AIR MICROBIOLOGY IN OPERATION- Before and after CleanAir placement	PARTICLE CONTROL - Before and after CleanAir placement
INM1	5 points per sample for mesophilic counts, yeasts and molds, coagulase + Staphylococci, Enterobacteriaceae, Klebsiella, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas a.	1 point in the center of the room + 1 point nozzle for colony counting at 30°C	1 point for colony count at 30°C	classification in at rest
INM2	5 points per sample for mesophilic counts, yeasts and molds, coagulase + Staphylococci, Enterobacteriaceae, Klebsiella, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas a.	1 point in the center of the room + 1 point nozzle for colony counting at 30°C	1 point for colony count at 30°C	classification in at rest

<p>INM3</p>	<p>5 points per sample for mesophilic counts, yeasts and molds, coagulase + Staphylococci, Enterobacteriaceae, Klebsiella, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas a.</p>	<p>1 point in the center of the room + 1 point nozzle for colony counting at 30°C</p>	<p>1 point for colony count at 30°C</p>	<p>classification in at rest</p>
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Table 4: Summary of testing sites @ INM

Furthermore, at INM various testing procedures will be conducted in order to test system usability and the performance in field. In particular, usability tests will be administered to both medical doctors and all the personnel of the clinical unit that will be in charge of using and managing the system. Performance in field will be also evaluated with medical doctors and medical personnel. Usability tests will consist of the use of a pre-defined form to be compiled by the medical personnel and doctors, depending on the site of installation. These forms will include also a dedicated section in which each compiler can suggest improvements or simply report negative experiences with the device.

The procedure will be followed by DPU and is therefore not outlined here again in detail. The main difference is that at the DPU the microbiological load in the air and at surfaces will only be determined by the overall number of CFUs without detailed specification of the different types itself. This is due to the fact that a possible decrease can be counted by the overall number of CFUs without the need for further quantification. DPU will focus on inorganic air quality parameters such as NO_x and O₃ concentration in the treatment room. The bacterial load at surfaces will be tested by adhesive film testing and in the air by air germ sampling.

7. Production End Control Testing & Requirements (VILL)

Before the delivery from the producer to the customer of the device following quality and performance testing has to be carried out:

- 48h continuous operating test
- Safety testing for high voltage in laboratory
- Measurement of voltage and current within specification limits
- Visual inspection of the device
- Verification that CE is attached
- Check of completeness of content of delivery package
- Correct packaging control
- User handbook/manual is provided with the device
- Installation instructions provided

8. Test Matrix for Field testing

Field testing is scheduled to start in July 2021 at both partner sites, provided the testing panels can be delivered in time by VILL

8.1. Tests and test matrix at DPU

Proposed size of flat test panel: DIN A3 / DIN A2; 2 of each

Wall- & ceiling mounted flat panels:

Test A: Performance in relation to panel size – with and without medical treatment

Test B: Performance in relation to installation location

Test C: Panel installed on ceiling directly above patient

3D-shaped panels:

Test D: Lamp-mounted panel with medical treatment

Test E: Double sided chair-mounted panel with medical treatment

Proposed size for 3D panels: 2 DIN A5 for chair; 1 DIN A4 for lamp

Airborne pathogens & particle count	Test A	Test B	Test C	Test D	Test E
without medical treatment	X	X		X	X
with medical treatment	X	X	X	X	X
Ozone & NOx measurement	X				
Operating time of system	X	X	X	X	X

Table 5: Preliminary test matrix for field tests @ DPU

8.2. Tests and test matrix at INM

Tests at INM will be performed mainly using three different environments, using the “ceiling tiles” installation mode. In particular, three tests will be performed:

Test A: medical office with at least one window (INM1);

Test B: medical office with no windows (INM2);

Test C: large waiting room (INM3).

The resulting test matrix is the following:

Airborne pathogens & particle count	Test A	Test B	Test C
without medical treatment	X	X	X
with medical treatment	X	X	
Ozone & NOx measurement	X	X	X
Operating time of system	X	X	X

Table 6: Preliminary test matrix for field tests @ INM